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QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE PENETRATION OF ADVANCED THERAPY MEDICINAL PRODUCTS IN EUROPE

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs) are innovative health technologies governed by a specialized regulatory framework due to their complexity, novelty, and potential impact on public health.

AIM: The aim of this work is to outline the quantitative characteristics and main therapeutic areas of ATMP application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A systematic review of ATMPs authorized through the centralized procedure of the European Medicines Agency was conducted.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION: As of November 2025, 30 ATMPs with granted marketing authorizations were identified. Gene therapies predominate (21/30; 70.0%), followed by somatic cell therapies (5/30; 16.7%), and tissue-engineered products (3/30; 10.0%). The ATMP portfolio shows a strong concentration in diseases with high unmet medical needs, reflected in the high proportion of orphan medicinal products (23/30; 76.7%) and therapies supported by accelerated regulatory pathways such as PRIME (17/30; 56.7%). This highlights the importance of regulatory mechanisms in fostering innovation and enabling earlier access to treatment.

An increasing trend in ATMP approvals is observed, particularly after 2018, indicating rapid biotechnological progress and enhanced translation of research into clinical practice. Therapeutic distribution is led by oncohematology and transplantation (40%), followed by inherited hematological and coagulation disorders (16.7%) and neurology (13.3%). These findings provide valuable insights for researchers and policymakers in prioritizing innovation funding and shaping public health strategies.

Keywords: *advanced therapy medicinal products, centralized authorization, gene therapy, orphan drugs, regulatory incentives, therapeutic distribution*